

1 **medAL-suite: a software solution for creating and deploying**

2 **complex clinical decision support algorithms**

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22 Abstract

23 **Background:** Sub-optimal quality of healthcare in low-resource settings is attributed in part
24 to poor adherence to clinical guidelines. Clinical decision support systems (CDSS) help to
25 integrate clinical guideline-based algorithms into logical workflows and improve adherence
26 to evidence-based recommendations, and hence quality of care. However, the process of
27 translating paper-based guidelines into electronic algorithmic formats is often complex,
28 inefficient, expensive, and error-prone due to reliance on advanced software developer
29 skills and clinical knowledge.

30 **Methods:** In response to these challenges, we developed an open-source software called
31 the Medical Algorithm Suite (*medAL-suite*), consisting of four components with a primary
32 goal of increasing efficiency, accuracy, and transparency of CDSS creation by giving
33 experienced clinicians, rather than software developers, greater control over the process.
34 At the heart of the software suite is the *medAL-creator* that allows clinicians to design
35 algorithms using a code-free drag-and-drop interface. Algorithms are subsequently
36 automatically deployed in *medAL-reader* to service level clinicians in health facilities. CDSS
37 implementers use *medAL-data* and *medAL-hub* to manage configuration, versioning, and
38 deployment.

39 **Results:** Since its development, the *medAL-suite* has been used to digitalize complex
40 primary care guidelines and deployed in large-scale clinical studies in Tanzania, Rwanda,
41 Kenya, Senegal, and India, leading to notable outcomes such as the reduction of
42 inappropriate antibiotic prescriptions and improvement in care quality. Nearly 300,000

43 pediatric outpatient consultations have been completed in Rwanda and Tanzania to date
44 using the digital algorithm.

45 **Discussion:** The medAL-*suite* focused on democratized development, process-centric
46 design, point-of-care utility, touch-screen interfaces, low cost, and low power consumption
47 to contribute to sustainable digital systems in low-resource settings. Important future
48 developments and adaptations as the software evolves should emphasize interoperability
49 and scalability, primarily via integrating CDSS functionality into electronic medical records
50 for a streamlined user experience that supports improved service quality at the point-of-
51 care.

52 **Keywords:** Clinical decision support, algorithm, digital health, clinical guidelines, CDSS

53 Background

54 Sub-optimal quality of healthcare in low-resource settings is attributed in part to
55 inaccurate diagnoses, inappropriate or unnecessary treatments and inadequate or unsafe
56 clinical practice [1]. Clinical guidelines synthesize medical evidence and expert opinion into
57 actionable information [2], and when adhered to, can standardize patient management and
58 improve quality of care [3]. However, adherence to paper-based guidelines, particularly in
59 outpatient settings, is typically low [4–5] due to their narrative nature and typical focus on a
60 single condition [2], whereas patients often present with multiple complaints, requiring
61 complex integration of several guidelines [4–5]. In recent years, electronic clinical decision
62 support systems (CDSS) have shown promise in achieving a complex integration of
63 primarily knowledge-based diagnostic algorithms into logical workflows, guiding clinicians
64 through patient consultations to recommended diagnoses and treatments. CDSS have
65 demonstrated improved adherence to guidelines [6–8], reduced antibiotic prescriptions [9–
66 11], and better clinical outcomes [8–9], albeit often in research conditions.

67 Despite the potential benefits for patients and health systems, the process of
68 translating paper-based clinical guidelines into electronic formats is often complex and
69 inefficient, especially for complex algorithms. To help address this problem, WHO
70 developed Standards-based, Machine-readable, Adaptive, Requirements-based, and
71 Testable (SMART) guidelines to guide CDSS developers and implementers through a 5-
72 step process of translating evidence-based narrative guidelines (L1) into operational,
73 software-neutral documentation of operational and functional requirements (L2), machine-

74 readable structured specifications, code, terminology and interoperability standards (L3),
75 software able to execute static algorithms and interoperable digital components (L4), and
76 finally executable dynamic algorithms trained and optimized with advanced analytics (L5)
77 [12]. Each step of this process requires advanced IT expertise and know how. The coded
78 clinical logic can be complex and difficult to understand, making stakeholder review and
79 validation slow and error-prone, and limiting the capacity for updates to keep up with
80 advances in medical evidence and guidelines [4–5]. It further increases the dependence of
81 digital health systems on advanced software developer skills that for now tend to remain
82 concentrated in the Global North, thereby keeping the cost of implementation and
83 maintenance of CDSS high and inhibiting autonomy of digital systems in low-resource
84 settings.

85 In response to these challenges, a unique open-source software called the Medical
86 Algorithm Suite (<https://medal-suite.com/>) was developed. The primary goal of the *medAL-*
87 *suite* is to increase efficiency, accuracy, and transparency of the L2 to L4 conversion
88 process for CDSS (Figure 1). The target users of the software suite include: 1) health
89 program-level clinicians who normally design or update algorithms (users of *medAL-*
90 *creator*); 2) service-level clinicians who benefit from decision support logic in their daily
91 clinical practice (users of *medAL-reader*); and 3) implementers or deployment managers of
92 CDSS who manage the configuration and deployment of IT tools in health facilities, create
93 and maintain users, and monitor performance of the system (users of *medAL-data* and
94 *medAL-hub*).

Using the medAL-suite, clinicians can create content themselves using an L2-like graphical interface and translation to L3 and L4 is done automatically.

Using the traditional pathway, translation from L2 to L3 requires extensive interaction between clinicians and programmers and transformation from L3 to L4 further programming skills are required.

95
 96 **Figure 1:** Digital algorithm creation (solid line arrows) and adaptation (dashed line arrows)
 97 process following a traditional pathway (bottom) and using the medAL-suite (top). Icons
 98 were obtained from the Noun Project (CC BY 3.0) <https://thenounproject.com> and
 99 <https://healthicons.org>.

100 With a code-free interface, health program-level clinicians can create complex
 101 decision logic tailored to local guidelines, epidemiology, and implementation context using
 102 their clinical decision logic skills without advanced programming skills (Figure 2). Clinical
 103 elements are defined within the design environment (medAL-creator) and decision logic is
 104 created using a drag-and-drop approach. The algorithms are deployed in an Android
 105 tablet-based application (medAL-reader), while preserving a logical consultation flow for
 106 end-users – such as nurses or clinical officers in health facilities. medAL-data is a database
 107 and hosting platform that facilitates the deployment process by enabling functions like
 108 creation of unique health facility identifiers, facility-specific algorithm versions, user

109 assignments, device allocations, algorithm setups, performance monitoring and
110 troubleshooting. *medAL-hub* is a local server based in health facilities that enables
111 communication among multiple devices via a local network to support task-shifting and
112 team-based care. It enables multiple users to access and update the same medical case in
113 sequence (Figure 2).

114 The software solution is designed for low-resource settings to run on inexpensive,
115 low power, widely available hardware. It can be deployed in two modes: client-server (with
116 *medAL-hub*) or standalone (without *medAL-hub*), depending on the implementation setting.
117 In standalone mode, tablets (*medAL-reader*) communicate directly with *medAL-data*,
118 whereas in client-server mode, many functions are facilitated by the *medAL-hub* (Figure 2).
119 Each of the four main components of the *medAL-suite* is further detailed in the subsequent
120 sections.

121

122 **Figure 2:** Overview of the main components of the medAL-suite and their configuration
 123 within the health system. Client-server mode of operation is shown (with medAL-hub).

124 Icons were obtained from the Noun Project (CC BY 3.0) <https://thenounproject.com> and
 125 <https://healthicons.org>.

126 **medAL-creator**

127 **Concept and definitions**

128 The goal of medAL-creator is to enable building complex diagnostic decision tree
 129 algorithms and package them for deployment to the end-user (service level clinician) in
 130 medAL-reader. medAL-creator uses the Ruby on Rails framework for its backend, React for
 131 its frontend development and a PostgreSQL database. In the platform, a user is assigned
 132 to a *project*, which contains one or more *algorithms* used for versioning. An *algorithm* is a
 133 series of decision trees. A *decision tree* is a component of the algorithm consisting of a set

134 of *variables* linked together through decision logic to reach a *diagnosis* as a terminal node
135 or endpoint (Figure 3). Decision trees are designed individually, and lead to one or more
136 diagnoses. Decision trees are also designed for each individual diagnosis to propose
137 *treatments* and *managements*. Treatment decision trees consider patient characteristics,
138 other diagnoses and treatment availability. Once the full *algorithm* (all decision trees and
139 links among them) is designed and configured, medAL-creator builds a JavaScript Object
140 Notation file (JSON), an open standard file format using human readable text to store and
141 transmit data objects. The JSON file is fed into medAL-reader to display the clinical
142 decision support logic to the end-user in a health facility. A significant advantage for the
143 users of medAL-creator is interacting with simpler, individual decision trees for groups of
144 clinical syndromes or diagnoses rather than the whole, complex algorithm of all possible
145 diagnoses at once. The flip side of this advantage is the difficulty in detecting conflicts
146 among diagrams due to the inability to see the entire algorithm at once. There currently
147 isn't a known solution that overcomes this challenge for very large and complex diagnostic
148 algorithms. The combination of medAL-creator and medAL-reader simplifies the user
149 experience by synthesizing the complexity of the full algorithm content and presenting it to
150 the end-user in a logical consultation flow.

151 ***Design area and mechanics***

152 The diagram creation page consists of a repository of *building blocks* and a *diagram area*.
153 Users drag and drop building blocks from the repository into the diagram area and connect
154 them with arrows to define the decision logic. The building block categories include
155 variables for patient clinical characteristics (e.g., demographic information, medical history

156 such as exposures and chronic conditions, symptoms and physical exam findings for the
157 current medical problem), “predefined syndromes” (i.e., sub-diagrams consisting of a
158 predefined combination of several variables), diagnoses, treatments, and managements
159 (Table 1). In a diagnostic algorithm, a basic diagram has one or more diagnoses as its
160 terminal nodes. Other building blocks are linked together to reach the diagnoses (Figure 3).
161 The logical operator AND is represented by linking two building blocks sequentially; the OR
162 operator, always interpreted as an inclusive OR, is represented by parallel branches. Age
163 cutoffs can be set for each arrow to define specific age conditioning. Managements and
164 medicines associated with each diagnosis, as well as chronic or past medical conditions
165 that may modify its severity or treatment plan, are built using a separate treatment diagram
166 that is linked to and can be opened from the diagnosis in Figure 3.

167

168 Table 1: Building blocks and element types in medAL-creator

Type	Description	Attributes	Example usage
Variable			
Demographic	Personal information that may or may not be used in diagrams (some used for identification)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Answer types (binary, categorical, integer, decimal, formula, date, string) - Complaint category - Body organ system - Indicates emergency? - Is mandatory? - Is linked to patient identity? - Value can be not feasible, unavailable, or unknown - Label, description and accompanying media (image, video, sound) - Lower and upper limits for clinically relevant warning (e.g., oxygen saturation of 88% is low warranting referral) - Lower and upper limits for possible data entry errors (e.g., weight of 1 kg for a 5-year-old child is not possible) 	Date of birth, sex, village of residence
Basic measurement	Routine body measurements taken during consultation; used in calculations		Weight, height, MUAC
Symptom	Based on the subjective report from a patient or caregiver		Cough, diarrhea, runny nose
Physical exam	Based on the physical examination performed by the clinician		Enlarged lymph nodes, jaundice
Vital sign	Important vital measurements that are often assessed before the consultation		Temperature, respiratory rate
Unique triage	Symptoms or signs triggering an expedited consultation to manage an emergency		Convulsing, unconscious
Exposure	Potential contact with a source of infection or toxicity		Risk factors for vertical HIV transmission, dog/bat bite, recent close contact with TB patient
Chronic condition	A long-standing, persistent disease that can impact how the case is managed		Cerebral palsy, sickle cell disease
Background calculation	Calculation performed using previously entered numerical variables		Weight-for-age or weight-for-height z-score
Assessment or test	A paraclinical test performed to aid in the diagnosis or detection of disease		Rapid diagnostic test, laboratory test, x-ray
Treatment condition	Additional question asked before the treatment section to account for limitations that impact management	Is ceftriaxone available? Can the patient swallow?	
Medical condition			
Predefined syndrome	Sub-diagram (or calculated variable based on combination of other variables) that decongests the visual display, makes it easier to reuse content, and gives the user ability to create scores	- Cutoff values used to set thresholds and assign weights to variables to calculate a severity score.	Dehydration risk score, moderate or severe malnutrition, Cape Town Clinical Decision Rule (CDR)
Diagnosis			
Diagnosis	A diagram can contain one or more diagnoses; diagnosis exclusions can also be applied (so that a more severe diagnosis, e.g., severe anemia excludes a milder diagnosis e.g., mild/moderate anemia).	- Level of urgency (1-10)	Severe anemia, pneumonia, malaria
Management			
Management	Non-pharmaceutical actions recommended for the clinical case, such as immediate actions, counselling, follow-up or referral.	- Level of urgency (1-10)	Urgent referral, give salbutamol now, ensure adequate fluid intake at home, follow up in 3 days
Treatment			
Medicine	Automated medicine dosing recommendation, using two approaches: calculated and fixed. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For calculated dosing, the user selects the formulation, and for each formulation the appropriate information (e.g., administration route, number per day, volume, maximum daily dose, etc.). - For fixed-dose, only administration route, number per day and number of applications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formulations (tablet, capsule, syrup, suspension, suppository, drops, solution, powder for injection, patch, cream, ointment, gel, spray, inhaler, pessary, dispersible tablet, lotion). - Breakability attribute for tablets (possible values: in 2, in 4, not breakable) 	Amoxicillin 250 mg tablet for the treatment of bacterial pneumonia: administer orally, 2x per day, maximal dose 100 mg/kg/day, tablet breakable in 2, duration 5 days.

169

170 **Figure 3:** An example of a diagnostic diagram for pharyngitis [A]; expanded definition of a
 171 scored predefined syndrome Cape Town clinical decision rule (CDR) [B]; and treatment
 172 diagram for the management of bacterial acute pharyngitis [C]. Note: CDR definition is
 173 adapted to consider tonsillar swelling, which must be present, separately in panel A, in
 174 addition to at least one of the other signs or symptoms included in the CDR in panel B.

175 *Configuration*

176 After building all the individual diagnostic algorithms, variables can be assigned to
 177 consultation stages, and further arranged in a specific sequence, which determines in what
 178 order they appear. Variables (or entire diagrams) can further be assigned to complaint
 179 categories (further described in the *medAL-reader* section), which are selected at the start
 180 of the consultation by the end-user based on the main presenting symptoms and serve as
 181 entry points into specific diagrams. It is possible to download a data dictionary with all

182 variable definitions, as well as to download and upload a full translation file in .xlsx format to
183 facilitate deployment of the clinical content in multiple languages.

184 *Unique feature highlights*

185 *Versioning:* A user of medAL-creator can maintain multiple versions of an algorithm by
186 copying the entire set of decision trees and making any number of desired modifications. A
187 specific version of an algorithm can be assigned to an individual health facility in medAL-
188 data, making it possible to deploy algorithms adapted to their unique setting (e.g., malaria
189 endemicity, level of resources). Algorithm version is subsequently reported in medAL-data
190 with each completed medical case.

191 *User notification:* When modifying a particular variable, the user is notified where in the
192 algorithm that variable is used, prompting an evaluation of the impact of the change.
193 However, referential integrity mechanisms are also in place, forbidding changes on
194 variables used in a version that is (or ever has been) deployed in the field.

195 *Exclusions:* Exclusions for diagnoses can be set in two ways: by drawing arrows between
196 diagnoses that exclude each other within a diagram; or by specifying the exclusion on a
197 dedicated page for diagnoses that exclude each other across different diagrams. For
198 instance, pneumonia would exclude “common cold” in case the patient presentation met
199 criteria for both diagnoses. Similar logic is applied to establishing a hierarchy of medicines
200 and managements. For example, it is possible for a child to have severe pneumonia, for
201 which the algorithm prompts to administer injectable gentamicin and ampicillin and to refer
202 the patient urgently to a hospital, and a concurrent milder diagnosis such as complicated

203 acute ear infection for which oral amoxicillin and home-based care are recommended. In
204 such cases, the *medAL-creator* user can set injectable ampicillin and gentamicin to
205 override oral amoxicillin and urgent referral to override home-based care so as not to
206 provide unnecessary, redundant or conflicting recommendations to the end-user.

207 *Automated validation checks:* Every time a new element is added to a diagram, the system
208 checks for consistency within the diagram. As an example, if the symptom sore throat
209 wasn't connected to the following question in the pharyngitis diagram (Figure 3), this would
210 trigger an alert prompting the user to check the algorithm and make sure that there are no
211 "floating" variables without links, resulting in a dead-end. The system also detects attempts
212 to create circular references.

213 ***medAL-reader***

214 *Overview*

215 The goal of *medAL-reader* is to offer the clinical end-users a comprehensive tool that
216 guides them through a patient consultation to one or several diagnoses and the
217 corresponding management plan. *medAL-reader* is built using the widely used JavaScript
218 framework React Native, enabling the use of a single codebase for both iOS and Android
219 platforms. The workflow is organized into the following consultation stages: registration,
220 initial assessment, consultation, assessments and tests, diagnoses, treatments and
221 managements, as per a typical outpatient consultation workflow. Presently, the application
222 is configured to store and display historical patient consultations, with the ability to search
223 for an existing patient using a name or a Quick Response (QR) code and add a new

224 consultation to his/her patient record. Prior to starting to use the application, the user can
225 select the desired language (of those into which the algorithm content has been translated
226 in *medAL-creator*) in the 'Settings' page.

227 ***Question sequence***

228 Question sequence is defined at several levels, including the consultation stage, complaint
229 category, and to some extent algorithm logic. At the highest level, questions are allocated
230 to consultation stages to align with the healthcare provider's typical workflow, or order in
231 which consultations are conducted. Within the consultation stages, questions are further
232 organized according to the complaint category to which the corresponding algorithm has
233 been assigned. For example, the outpatient algorithm used in Rwanda and Tanzania to
234 treat children between 2 months and 14 years of age includes 9 complaint categories:
235 Fever, Respiratory, Gastrointestinal, Ear/Nose/Mouth/Throat, Eye, Neurological, Skin/hair,
236 Genitourinary, and Accident/Musculoskeletal (Figure 4; panel 1). Additionally, the algorithm
237 contains questions asked to every patient, regardless of their main presenting complaint,
238 as required by relevant clinical guidelines, for triage purposes for instance. While the
239 consultation stages are currently hard-coded in *medAL-reader*, complaint categories can
240 be defined by the user in *medAL-creator* according to the type of algorithm being designed.
241 In theory, all inputs in the application are mandatory; however, provisions have been made
242 to accommodate some measurements that are sometimes not feasible to perform (e.g.,
243 weight, height, MUAC, respiratory rate in Figure 4; panels 2 and 5). For these, the
244 healthcare provider can mark that the measurement is not feasible to ascertain, with
245 modifications made in the algorithm to adapt to the missing information.

246 *Unique feature highlights*

247 *Error and warning messages:* As described in Table 1, when variables are created, two
248 types of thresholds are set for numerical variables, one to indicate a clinically relevant
249 warning to prompt healthcare provider action (e.g., low MUAC warranting referral to a
250 malnutrition program, Figure 4; panel 2), and another to indicate a probable erroneous
251 value that should be revisited and corrected (e.g., oxygen saturation of 20%). The
252 messaging helps to improve data quality and compliance with clinical protocols.

253 *Information buttons:* Elements in the algorithm can be accompanied with additional text,
254 images, sound clips, gif animations or mp4 videos that are accessible via an “i”
255 (information) button that appears next to the element (Figure 4). This content can serve as
256 learning material (e.g., an image that helps to identify a particular skin condition) or a
257 reminder (e.g., a list of symptoms for which to bring a child back to the health facility) to the
258 healthcare provider.

259 *Ability to accept or reject diagnoses and treatments:* Healthcare provider autonomy has
260 been described as a major barrier to acceptability and use of digital health tools [13–15].
261 As such, medAL-reader allows the users to agree or disagree with one or more of the
262 proposed diagnoses and treatments, or to select another diagnosis in place of the
263 proposed ones. The user can select from a drop-down menu another diagnosis that is
264 present in the algorithm and thus receive the relevant management and treatment
265 recommendations, or add a custom diagnosis entered as free text for documentation
266 purposes, for which management and treatment recommendations are not provided by the

267 system (Figure 4; panels 6 and 7). The same mechanism of agreeing, disagreeing, or
268 manually adding (from the dropdown list with dosing information or as free text without
269 dosing information) applies to medicines. This also serves as feedback to algorithm
270 developers, signaling to review clinical content and determine whether adaptation to a
271 specific clinical context (e.g., medicine availability) or additional training or supportive
272 supervision (e.g., for inappropriate addition of antibiotics) may be needed.

273

274 Figure 4: Progression of the consultation workflow in medAL-reader (some screens
275 omitted).

276 **medAL-*data***

277 medAL-*data* has two main objectives: first, it facilitates a secure deployment of clinical
278 algorithms on electronic devices in health facilities; and second, it hosts the clinical data
279 generated through its regular use (Table 2). medAL-*data* is developed with the Laravel
280 framework and a PostgreSQL database, running on a NGINX web server. Among the
281 different packages used in the application, the most significant ones are: AdminLTE to
282 develop the user interface, Passport to secure the exchanges of data with medAL-*reader*
283 and medAL-*creator*, Laravel Auditing to monitor and supervise changes in the database,
284 Google2FA for Laravel to implement two-factor authentication, and Laravel-permission to
285 define user roles and permissions. The database follows an entity-attribute-value (EAV)
286 model; this characteristic is required by the fact that medAL-*creator* generates a dynamic
287 data structure (as the user can add or remove variables in various algorithm versions at
288 any time), meaning that the collector of the data needs to be dynamic as well.

289 The heart of the software is what is called a loader; its role is to process all JSON
290 data files received from medAL-*reader*, perform quality checks, and load them in the data
291 model. The loader is updated at regular intervals through an API available in medAL-
292 *creator* in order to always be up-to-date with the latest version of the algorithm. In case of a
293 failed process, the JSON is moved to another folder (failed folder) and the data manager
294 can manually analyze the medical cases that failed to load in the database to understand
295 any inconsistencies.

296 The deployment manager can create health facilities, devices (tablets and local
297 raspberry pi servers called hubs), and users (healthcare workers), and assign devices,
298 users and algorithm versions (from *medAL-creator*) to health facilities in *medAL-data*.
299 Within the health facility management page, it is also possible to generate unique patient ID
300 labels (QR codes) for printing in case patient identification is required by the
301 implementation scenario.

302 The deployment manager can also monitor the data flow based on the most recent
303 sync dates, as well as the status of devices, particularly the hubs, to make sure that the
304 most recent updates have been deployed. In case of outdated devices, it is possible to
305 access error messages for updates that failed to deploy to determine if a manual push of
306 updates or a field visit to the health facility is needed. Management of security features,
307 such as device pin codes and authentication tokens that allow devices to communicate
308 with *medAL-data* are also supported.

309 The data management functionalities include exporting data in relational or flat .csv
310 formats, dropping of medical cases, patients (with their associated medical cases) or entire
311 health facilities (with their associated patients and medical cases) from analysis, and
312 reviewing patient and medical case duplicates. Medical case duplicates are automatically
313 flagged based on multiple consultations created for the same patient on the same day. The
314 data manager can review two cases at a time side by side and retain the more complete
315 entry, while the other is marked as 'duplicates' and subsequently dropped from the
316 database. Patient duplicates are flagged based on matching first and last name and/or date
317 of birth; optionally deduplication can be done on any other relevant variable such as the

318 national ID number. Similarly, two patients can be compared side by side in terms of
 319 demographics (e.g., village of residence, name of the caregiver) and either merged or kept
 320 separate. When patients are merged, a new 'active' patient is created, while the duplicate
 321 patients are marked as 'merged'. Going forward, the new 'active' patient carries the links to
 322 the medical cases from both merged patients to enable a cohort analysis of all
 323 consultations for a given patient.

324 **Table 2:** Main features of *medAL-data*

Security
User rights management
Passport authentication
Deployment
Create health facilities with attributes (country, region, GPS coordinates)
Create devices (tablets and hubs) with attributes (model, operating system, MAC address)
Create medical staff users with attributes (cadre)
Assign and manage devices and users associated with each health facility
Assign and manage algorithm versions (from <i>medAL-creator</i>) in each health facility
Generate unique IDs (QR codes) specific to each health facility
IT system monitoring
Load data coming from <i>medAL-reader</i> and store them in the data model
Monitor data flow from health facilities (time stamps of last synced cases)
Access information about JSON files of medical cases that failed to load in the database
Monitor update status of hubs and tablets (to verify all updates have been deployed)
In case of outdated devices, access error messages for updates that failed to deploy
Assign access tokens to all devices to authorize communication with <i>medAL-data</i> (security feature)
Assign a unique 4-digit passcode to each health facility to unlock tablets (security feature)
Data management
View patients, medical cases, diagnoses, and medications, linked by unique medical case ID
Identify duplicate cases, compare them side by side and remove one case based on completeness
Identify duplicate patients (same patient registered multiple times) and merge them
Drop individual medical cases, patients, or health facilities (in a cascade manner) from analysis
Export data in relational and flat .csv formats (de-identified and identified exports available)

325

326 *medAL-hub*

327 *medAL-hub* facilitates the client-server mode (versus standalone mode) of operation,
 328 providing local hosting of the health facility database and the ability of multiple users

329 (tablets) to access and update medical cases. *medAL-hub* is developed with the Laravel
330 framework and a PostgreSQL database. The application has no user interface and runs on
331 a NGINX web server hosted on a Raspberry Pi (HyprIoTOS). The primary use case for this
332 feature is task-shifting among several clinical users on different devices to update or
333 manage the same medical case: for example, a patient is registered at the registration
334 window (user 1), vital signs and basic measurements are entered at the triage station (user
335 2), and the rest of the consultation is completed by the clinician in the consultation room
336 (user 3).

337 Client-server and standalone modes have their advantages and disadvantages
338 (Table 3) and selection of the appropriate mode highly depends on the implementation
339 context. The IT configuration is flexible as the mode of operation can be determined on an
340 individual health facility basis. For example, in large health facilities with multiple
341 consultation rooms and/or multiple potential users and a relatively stable power supply
342 (short power outages of less than 2 hours), the client-server mode may be more
343 appropriate. On the other hand, in small health facilities with a single user and prolonged
344 power outages, standalone mode may be preferred. While both configurations allow for
345 offline use of the system for patient management, the raspberry pi and router must have a
346 power supply for the client-server mode to work as intended. During power outages, the
347 tablet can be temporarily used in pseudo-standalone mode, with cases syncing to the hub
348 when power to the hub and router is restored.

349 **Table 3:** Characteristics in the form of advantages [+] and disadvantages [-] of client-
350 server (with medAL-*hub*) and standalone (without medAL-*hub*) modes of IT deployment

Client-server

- [+] Possible to access and update a medical case on multiple tablets (task-shifting; patient history)
 - [+] One sim card (for router) is needed per health facility – easier to manage and maintain
 - [+] Tablet storage (and clearing storage for troubleshooting) is not an issue
 - [+] More reliable in terms of data storage (PostgreSQL)
 - [-] High dependency on power supply (including with back-up battery or UPS)
 - [-] Higher complexity requires more advanced IT skills to set up, maintain and troubleshoot
-

Standalone

- [+] Low dependency on power supply (power bank is sufficient to charge the tablet)
 - [-] Tablet storage can become an issue as medical cases accumulate
 - [-] If clearing storage is needed for trouble-shooting purposes, all patient history is lost as well
 - [-] Patient history is stored in one tablet (problematic in health facilities with multiple consultation rooms)
 - [-] Multiple sim cards (or Wi-Fi network) needed for syncing if multiple tablets are used in a health facility
-

351

352 **Discussion**

353 The primary goal of many digital health technologies is to enable clinicians to provide better
354 services at the point-of-care. Clinical decision support is among the key functionalities of
355 digital technologies aimed at impacting quality of healthcare. The medAL-*suite* was created
356 to deliver on this primary goal [16], focusing on democratized development, process-
357 centric design, point-of-care utility, touch-screen interface, low cost, and low power
358 consumption. These themes aim to create sustainable digital systems that enhance
359 healthcare delivery and outcomes in low-resource environments by aligning better with
360 their specific needs and resource constraints.

361 First, by design, medAL-*creator* is process- and guideline-centric, prioritizing the actual
362 workflows and clinical guidelines involved in delivering healthcare, rather than focusing on
363 data collection and administrative tasks such as billing. It further aims to democratize the
364 clinical decision support development process by putting clinical content creation primarily

365 in the hands of clinicians rather than IT specialists. By transforming complex code into
366 graphical representations, decision logic becomes more comprehensible and easily
367 modifiable by those who are closest to its utilization. Reducing the need for clinicians and
368 software developers to find a common language to understand clinical and technical
369 requirements increases the speed of content development and adaptation and has the
370 potential to reduce errors. Second, *medAL-reader* is intended for use at the point-of-care
371 on touch-screen devices to facilitate an intuitive user experience. Third, low-cost and low-
372 power technologies are prioritized in the deployment, particularly by using Raspberry Pis in
373 the client-server configuration.

374 Since its development, the *medAL-suite* has been used to digitalize complex primary care
375 guidelines and deployed in large-scale clinical studies in Tanzania, Rwanda, Kenya,
376 Senegal, and India, leading to notable outcomes such as the reduction of inappropriate
377 antibiotic prescriptions and improvement in care quality [11, 17]. Nearly 300,000 pediatric
378 outpatient consultations have been completed in Rwanda and Tanzania to date using the
379 digital algorithm. By allowing clinical logic to be visualized and edited through *medAL-*
380 *creator*, the system has empowered healthcare providers to adapt the decision support
381 logic to their specific contexts, thereby enhancing relevance and improving adherence.
382 Despite these successes, integrating new technologies within existing health systems
383 presents challenges related to policy alignment and accountability. The balance between
384 innovation and regulatory compliance remains a critical area that requires ongoing
385 attention and dialogue among stakeholders.

386 Despite its advantages, *medAL-creator* also has some limitations and areas for future
387 development. From a technical standpoint, *medAL-creator*'s approach to individual
388 decision trees means that users need to mentally track multiple diagrams to identify
389 potential conflicts among them. Additionally, this structure does not allow for viewing the
390 algorithm from start to finish, potentially hindering a holistic view of the diagnostic process.
391 Another consideration is that while a diagram can contain one or more diagnoses, each
392 diagnosis still requires a separate treatment diagram.

393 From the sustainability standpoint, priority axes of focus for development include
394 interoperability, scalability, and dynamic algorithms. The development of an authoring tool
395 that enables clinicians and governments to manage, exchange, validate, and implement
396 digital clinical guidelines, accessible by any point-of-care system, appears to be the optimal
397 solution for accommodating the needs of diverse local settings. As implementation of
398 electronic medical records (EMR) becomes more commonplace, it is critical to consider
399 integration of clinical decision support within these systems. The lack of interoperability with
400 reporting systems also means manual data entry and extraction from paper files and
401 registries and double data entry into existing EMR systems, introducing additional burden
402 for health workers. While simple decision logic can be programmed directly in EMR
403 software, a tool like *medAL-creator* can help with authoring complex logic that can be
404 integrated into the medical record workflow.

405 *Interoperability:* Adopting standards and best practices such as HL7/FHIR, HL7/CQL, and
406 mapping data elements and clinical concepts to standard terminologies such as Open
407 Concept Lab (OCL) will empower CDSS implementers to use *medAL-creator* for creating

408 and adapting content based on local or WHO standard digital clinical guidelines. This
409 interoperability is crucial for integrating systems, allowing authors to develop clinically
410 secure and transparent algorithms. Consequently, it enables scalability across various
411 environments without the need for extensive customization by creating sharable content.

412 *Scalability:* Using a central authoring tool such as *medAL-creator* empowers governments
413 and local authorities to determine their desired deployment strategies. This approach
414 reduces dependence on external entities and infrastructure, with the only requirement
415 being the ability to use the output from the authoring tool in their own front-end application
416 deployed at the point of service (e.g., EMR).

417 *Dynamic algorithms:* At present, *medAL-suite* supports the creation and deployment of
418 knowledge-based CDSS that derive the decision based on a set of pre-defined rules, as
419 opposed to non-knowledge based CDSS that model the decision based on available data
420 [18]. However, the vast data collected through the *medAL-suite* presents a significant
421 opportunity to leverage it to enhance algorithm performance and personalization. By
422 applying advanced analytics, such as Modular Clinical Decision Support Networks (MoDN)
423 – a novel decision tree composed of flexible neural network modules to facilitate diagnostic
424 predictions [19], the *medAL-suite* could potentially move beyond the typical knowledge-
425 based "one-size-fits-all" approach, adapting more dynamically to patient-specific factors
426 and local epidemiological trends.

427

428

429 Conclusion

430 The medAL-*suite* is a useful clinician-centric technology aimed at increasing the speed and
431 transparency with which digital clinical decision support systems implemented. As the tool
432 evolves, the emphasis will remain on adaptations that not only meet the current demands
433 of healthcare providers but also anticipate future challenges and opportunities in global
434 health. With a commitment to innovation, interoperability, and impact, the medAL-*suite* can
435 play a significant role in transforming healthcare delivery in low-resource settings, in line
436 with the vision of an ecosystem of digital tools that respond to changing treatment
437 guidelines and plug into standard-based health records that support the patient over time
438 and across health system interactions [20].

439

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